

Beyond Corrosion: Autonomous Real-Time Detection of Structural Cracks and Degradation Using Robotic Sensing and Digital Twins

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Abstract

Structural crack detection and environmental hazard monitoring are essential in non-destructive testing (NDT) for civil infrastructure. This paper presents a real-time, AI-powered multi-sensor dashboard that receives data from a mobile climbing robot. The system integrates optical, thermal infrared (IR), and gas sensing, each supported by dedicated deep learning models. AI inference is performed server-side to classify surface cracks, segment IR-based crack regions, and detect gas anomalies. Models include MobileNetV2 for crack classification, U-Net for IR segmentation, and a gas classifier using MQ-135 data. The dashboard fuses predictions with visual overlays and quantitative measurements, enabling faster, safer, and more robust infrastructure inspection.

Keywords: Real-Time Infrastructure Inspection, Multi-Modal Sensing, Crack Detection, Gas Leak Monitoring, Climbing Robots, AI-Based Non-Destructive Testing (NDT)

1. Introduction

Civil structures such as bridges, buildings, and pipelines are prone to defects like cracks and leaks over time. Early detection of these faults is critical for ensuring safety and supporting preventive maintenance [1]. Traditional NDT methods relying on human inspectors or handheld devices are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and sometimes hazardous, especially when assessing high facades or confined spaces [2]. Furthermore, single-sensor approaches often encounter limitations due to environmental conditions: visible-light cameras may fail in poor lighting or cluttered scenes, while thermal or acoustic sensors alone may overlook certain defects [3].

To overcome these specific limitations of traditional and single-sensor methods, namely labor intensity, safety hazards, environmental sensitivity, and potential defect oversight, there is growing interest in multi-modal systems that combine complementary sensors to offer a more robust assessment of structural health [4]. Recent reviews highlight that multi-modal data fusion significantly improves the accuracy and reliability of crack detection by leveraging complementary sensor characteristics. However, many existing multi-modal solutions are computationally intensive, making them unsuitable for real-time applications in field inspections [5].

This work addresses this gap by developing a real-time, AI-powered multi-sensor inspection platform. Although the climbing robot hardware is still under development, the sensing and analysis system has been fully implemented and tested using publicly available real-world datasets [6][7]. We focus on two key NDT challenges: detecting structural cracks (in concrete or masonry) and identifying hazardous gas leaks in infrastructure. Cracks can jeopardize the stability of bridges and buildings [5], while gas leaks, such as from sewer lines or industrial zones, pose both safety and environmental risks [8]. To enable deployment in real-world infrastructure scenarios, particularly on vertical or hazardous surfaces, we integrate the sensing system onto a custom-built climbing robot. The goal of applying this robotic platform is to

provide safer, more effective, and remote access to inspection zones that are typically difficult for human inspectors to reach, such as bridge columns, high-rise facades, or industrial tanks.

The vertical mobility robot proposed in this study is a four-wheeled system that moves on vertical surfaces using vacuum adhesion generated by a centrally mounted radio-controlled (RC) fan. The single-board computer handles motor control and collects sensor data, which is transmitted via Wi-Fi to the external dashboard.

Our platform integrates an optical RGB camera, a thermal infrared (IR) camera, and a gas sensor (MQ-135), each paired with AI models tailored to its modality. The RGB camera captures high-resolution surface imagery for crack classification. The thermal IR camera detects potential subsurface or low-contrast cracks by identifying thermal discontinuities [9], and the gas sensor detects dangerous gases (e.g., CO₂, NH₃, benzene) often associated with structural degradation [10]. Beyond real-time detection, the platform currently supports pixel-level crack quantification and timestamp-based event tracking, with an architecture ready for future enhancements such as spatial localization, physical size calibration, and automated multi-modal sensor fusion to improve detection confidence.

This research is driven by the question: How can we design a real-time, AI-driven multi-sensor system that enhances the detection and characterization of structural cracks and hazardous gas leaks during civil infrastructure inspections, and can be deployed on a mobile climbing robot in the future?

We investigate whether the fusion of optical, thermal, and gas sensing modalities, combined with appropriate deep learning models, can provide a more comprehensive and efficient NDT of structures than single-sensor or offline methods. At this stage, while the climbing robot hardware is under development, the sensing and analysis system has been implemented and validated using real-world datasets and simulated operational scenarios. Our aim is to demonstrate that multi-modal data fusion in a real-time dashboard significantly improves the speed, safety, and reliability of inspections, while laying the foundation for future robotic field deployments.

To address this, we trained and evaluated both a custom CNN and MobileNetV2 architecture for optical crack detection using the SDNET2018 dataset. MobileNetV2 outperformed the CNN in terms of precision, recall, and inference speed, and was therefore selected for real-time deployment.

In the following sections, we describe the system architecture, robotic platform, sensor data sources, and the real-time inference pipeline for crack characterization and gas anomaly detection. We also compare our method to existing state-of-the-art approaches in the literature, including UAV-based crack inspection, thermal-vision fusion methods, and robotic gas leak detectors.

2. Literature Review

To position our work in context, we compare it against several state-of-the-art inspection methods from recent literature in terms of their practical deployment capabilities and diagnostic performance. Specifically, we analyze differences in sensor modalities, platform mobility (e.g.,

drones, ground robots, static setups), ability to perform real-time analysis in the field, and the precision or sensitivity of their detection outcomes. The system presented in this study uniquely combines three sensing modalities: optical (RGB), thermal (IR), and gas detection, within a single platform and delivers real-time analysis, whereas many existing approaches focus on only one or two modalities and rely on offline post-processing. Table 1 summarizes this comparative overview.

Table 1: Comparative overview of different NDT methods.

Approach & Source	Sensors	Detectable Target(s)	Platform / Mobility	Real-Time	Performance
System presented in this study	RGB camera, IR thermal, MQ-135 gas sensor	Surface cracks, subsurface thermal anomalies, gas hazards	Vertical-climbing robot for pillars, facades, or elevated surfaces	Yes – live Web-based dashboard	MobileNetV2 for crack classification (91% acc.); U-Net for thermal segmentation; pixel-level crack area; Random Forest for gas alerts; ~0.4–0.6s inference latency
UAV + Deep Learning [11]	Optical camera (RGB)	Surface cracks	UAV drone (aerial imagery)	No (offline processing after flight)	High crack detection accuracy (~95% precision); automated crack measurement using encoder–decoder CNN
"CrackNet-V" (Visible + Thermal Fusion) [9]	Optical camera (RGB), IR thermal camera	Surface and subsurface cracks	Static or vehicle-mounted	Partially (processing slower)	~5–10% improvement over RGB-only models; uses hierarchical attention CNN for fused segmentation
Gas Leak Detection (Multi-Modal) [8]	Gas sensors, Thermal camera	Gas leaks (e.g. CH ₄ , CO ₂)	Soft robot (pipeline crawler)	Yes – onboard AI	98.9% gas leak classification accuracy; lightweight model (115 MB) deployable in the field
RGB camera + acoustic array (112-channel) [12]	RGB camera + acoustic array (112-channel)	Gas leaks (pinhole, open-end), arc discharges (Corona, Surface, Floating)	Mobile robotic platform (indoor industrial)	Yes (~2.1 s inference)	Multi-modal fusion (vision + acoustic); Inception-style CNN; 99% gas leak detection; robust under noise/reverb; +44%p vs. baseline methods
Thermal Drone for Oil & Gas Pipeline Inspection [13]	Thermal camera	Surface cracks, pipeline gas leakages	UAV drone (risky/remote areas)	Yes (onboard, <100 ms delay)	High-precision AI classifier for cracks and leaks; real-time alerting; implemented with hardware parallel processing for on-board performance

Recent works like that of [7] have leveraged drones for crack inspection. UAVs capture high-resolution optical images of large structures, and a deep encoder–decoder CNN processes these images offline to detect and measure cracks with high precision (~95% accuracy). UAVs excel in rapidly covering large or hard-to-reach structures like bridge decks and towers. However, a major limitation is that inspection data is collected first and processed later—there is no real-time crack detection during the flight. Moreover, UAV-based methods typically rely solely on optical imaging; they do not incorporate thermal or gas sensing, meaning subsurface cracks or environmental hazards could be missed. While UAVs excel at wide-area scanning, they typically lack real-time processing and multi-modal cross-validation, limiting their responsiveness in complex environments. Our system, though more localized, allows immediate decisions on-site, with visual, thermal, and gas hazard information synchronized live.

[9] introduced a dual-modality crack detection approach, combining visible and thermal imagery to enhance crack recognition. Their method ("CrackNet-V") overlays thermal signatures onto RGB images and feeds them into a hierarchical attention CNN. The fusion improves detection accuracy by 5–10% compared to visible-only models. Thermal imagery compensates for lighting challenges by revealing cracks through heat flow patterns even under poor visual conditions [9]. While this fusion approach is like ours, there are key differences. CrackNet-V focuses purely on vision-based crack detection without environmental gas sensing. Additionally, their models are heavier, often requiring powerful GPUs and introducing latency unsuitable for fully real-time deployment. In contrast, our dashboard achieves continuous updates (~1–2 Hz) using optimized U-Net and lightweight classifiers. Mobility also differs: CrackNet-V is typically applied to stationary or slow-moving platforms (vehicles, handheld devices), while our system is integrated onto a mobile climbing robot that can traverse vertical surfaces.

[8] developed a real-time gas leak detection system for pipelines, using a combination of thermal imaging and gas sensor arrays on a soft robot crawler. Their deep learning pipeline achieved 98.9% classification accuracy, showing high reliability in identifying natural gas leaks. Their system also runs onboard, making it suitable for in-field deployment. Compared to their specialized leak detection platform, our system is broader: we monitor not only gas anomalies but also cracks in civil structures. However, our gas sensing module, based on a single MQ-135 sensor and basic classifier, is comparatively simpler than their multi-sensor, ensemble-based method optimized for gas classification [8].

Figure 1: Real-time multi-sensor inspection system. The climbing robot integrates RGB, thermal, and gas sensors, with AI inference modules feeding a live Web dashboard for crack detection and gas anomaly alerts.

In summary, existing state-of-the-art methods tend to excel in one domain: either vision-based crack detection or gas leak detection, often using a single modality or requiring offline analysis. The unique value of our system is in its integration of multiple sensing domains in real time on a single platform. While a UAV equipped a high-capacity CNN might find cracks over a whole bridge faster, and a specialized pipeline monitor might pinpoint leaks with extreme accuracy, our system aims to provide a one-stop solution for on-site inspectors to simultaneously catch different types of problems. This is particularly useful in complex scenarios like inspecting an old chemical plant structure, where you might have concrete columns that could be cracked (need vision/thermal) and pipelines or storage tanks that could leak (need gas sensing). Our system would allow an inspector to deploy one robot and get a comprehensive hazard report. The trade-off lies in prioritizing model efficiency over depth to maintain real-time responsiveness on the dashboard.

3. Methodology: System Overview and Architecture

The proposed system is a real-time, AI-powered multi-sensor inspection platform designed for future deployment on a mobile climbing robot. While the physical robot and sensors are still under development, the data processing and analysis pipeline has been fully implemented and tested using publicly available datasets that simulate the inputs of three sensing modalities: an optical RGB camera, a thermal infrared (IR) camera, and a gas sensor (MQ135).

The overall system architecture is illustrated in Figure 1. Each simulated sensor stream is routed through a dedicated inference module: RGB images are analyzed by a MobileNetV2-based crack classification model, thermal images are processed by a U-Net segmentation model to extract crack regions, and gas concentration values are fed into a lightweight classifier trained to detect anomalous readings of common hazardous gases such as CO₂, NH₃, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs).

All inference modules run in real time on a connected server or local machine. The outputs such as crack detection results, segmented masks, and gas risk levels, are forwarded to a web-based

dashboard, where they are visualized alongside the corresponding input data. This architecture mirrors how the complete system will operate in the field, where the climbing robot will transmit sensor data wirelessly to the dashboard via Wi-Fi.

The dashboard, implemented using the Streamlit framework [14], serves as the central user interface. It supports live visualization, sensor-specific module control, and real-time decision-making. Each sensor module can be toggled independently, allowing flexible workflows depending on the inspection context. For instance, an operator may begin by scanning a surface with the RGB module to detect visible cracks, then switch to the IR module to identify thermally distinct subsurface defects, all while monitoring gas sensor outputs for hazardous emissions.

To support practical deployment, we prioritized efficient model architectures and optimization strategies. MobileNetV2 was chosen for optical crack classification due to its favorable balance between accuracy and inference speed, making it suitable for consumer-grade hardware. Similarly, the U-Net segmentation model was optimized using moderate input resolutions and performance-tuned libraries to ensure fast prediction of thermal crack masks. Together, these models enable the system to deliver inference results with minimal latency, typically within 1–2 seconds of simulated sensor data input.

Figure 2: Real-time AI pipeline for infrastructure inspection. Simulated sensor data (optical, thermal, gas) is streamed into model inference modules (MobileNetV2, U-Net, Random Forest) and visualized in a unified Streamlit dashboard.

The dashboard also includes adjustable parameters for alert thresholds and polling frequencies. For example, users can configure gas concentration thresholds or crack confidence scores to trigger visual alerts. This dynamic and modular design allows inspectors to tailor the inspection session in real time, contrasting with traditional workflows where sensor data is collected separately and analyzed post-inspection [15].

By fusing multiple sensor modalities into a unified, real-time platform, the system enables immediate cross-validation of inspection results. A crack detected in RGB imagery can be verified through a corresponding thermal anomaly, while a sudden gas spike can be interpreted in the structural context. This integrated approach enhances the reliability, responsiveness, and safety of structural health assessments, paving the way for future deployment on mobile robotic platforms in complex inspection environments.

4. Robotic Platform for Vertical Mobility

Robots that move on vertical surfaces reduce the need for manual inspection of tall or unsafe structures [16]. This robot was built to collect data remotely from such surfaces.

4.1 Mechanical Design

The chassis is fabricated via fused deposition modeling (FDM) using polylactic acid (PLA). It employs a four-wheel configuration in a differential drive layout. Each wheel is independently powered by brushed DC motors (6V), allowing point turns and directional correction. Total platform weight is 1.6 kg including battery and payload. The wheelbase and center of gravity are optimized for stability during vertical operation [17].

4.2 Active Vacuum Adhesion and Vertical Mobility Technology

Adhesion is achieved using a 12-blade RC ducted fan that generates a contactless pressure differential. The fan continuously draws air from the cavity between the robot chassis and the surface, creating a low-pressure zone that enables the platform to remain suspended. Ambient air is pulled in through the gaps between the wheels and the surface, sustaining airflow without the need for direct sealing. Adhesion force depends on the fan's static pressure rating, airflow rate, and the geometry of the chassis-surface interface. The system operates at an average current of 2.6 A under load and requires uninterrupted suction for support. As the mechanism does not employ a sealed vacuum chamber, no leak compensation is required, but performance is sensitive to surface texture and chassis standoff height [18].

4.3 Electronics, Computation and Sensors:

The robot runs on a Raspberry Pi 3B, which handles motor control, sensor input, and Wi-Fi communication [19]. It uses a motor driver for the wheels and an ESC for the fan. Power comes from a 3-cell 7200 mAh LiPo battery (11.1 V), with a buck converter for 5V components. Sensors include an RGB camera, a thermal infrared camera, and an MQ-135 gas sensor.

4.4 Data Reception, Transmission, and Processing:

The robot designed to send sensor data such as RGB images, thermal visuals, and gas readings, over Wi-Fi to an external dashboard. This reduces the processing load on the onboard computer. Each data stream is timestamped and sent to modules that classify cracks, segment thermal images, or detect gas anomalies. The results appear on a web-based dashboard for live viewing. To avoid delays or dropouts, the system limits frame rates and buffers data to handle unstable connections [20].

5. Sensor Modalities and Data Sources

To effectively detect both structural cracks and hazardous gases, the system employs three primary sensor modalities, each paired with data-driven AI models:

5.1 Optical RGB Camera – MobileNetV2 Crack Classifier:

The RGB camera is intended to capture high-resolution color imagery of structural surfaces such as bridge decks, pavements, and walls. For crack detection, we employ a MobileNetV2-based image classifier trained on the SDNET2018 dataset, which includes over 56,000 labeled

images of cracked and intact concrete under varied real-world conditions, such as shadows, stains, surface irregularities, and lighting variations.

Compared to heavier CNNs like VGG16 [21], MobileNetV2 offers a significantly lighter architecture while maintaining high classification performance. In our experiments, the model achieved 91% accuracy, with 0.87 precision and 0.45 recall on cracked (CD) samples. This balance favors precision in crack identification while maintaining responsiveness for real-time deployment.

During inference, input frames are resized to 160×160 pixels and normalized before being passed to the model. The output is a binary prediction (crack or no crack), and high-confidence detections are logged for visualization on the dashboard as shown in Figures 3a-3c in Appendix. Although the model does not perform pixel-wise segmentation, optional interpretability tools like Grad-CAM or contour overlays can be applied to highlight likely crack regions in the image.

One key limitation of the optical modality is the lack of physical calibration: SDNET2018 does not include metadata such as focal length or real-world scale, so crack dimensions (e.g., length, width, area) are reported only in pixels. Accurate physical measurement would require additional calibration steps during field deployment.

Despite this limitation, the RGB modality offers strong performance for detecting surface-level cracks in good lighting conditions and serves as an effective first-pass filter. To address its limitations under poor lighting or surface ambiguity, the system incorporates thermal segmentation through the IR camera, discussed in Section 5.2.

5.2 Thermal IR Camera – U-Net Crack Segmentation:

The thermal infrared (IR) camera provides temperature-based imagery that is especially effective for detecting cracks through heat flow irregularities. Structural cracks typically disrupt thermal conductivity, leading to localized hot or cold spots that appear as linear anomalies in thermal images. These thermal patterns can indicate not only surface cracks but also subsurface or partially obscured defects, particularly when the structure has experienced heating or cooling cycles [9].

To segment cracks from thermal imagery, we trained a U-Net model on a pixel-wise annotated dataset derived from the work of Maguire et al. [7]. This dataset contains thousands of infrared images of concrete structures, with ground-truth masks identifying crack regions under a variety of environmental conditions. The U-Net learns to distinguish true crack signatures from thermal artifacts such as dirt, stains, or surface spalling.

The model accepts a thermal image as input and produces a binary mask that highlights detected crack regions. Unlike RGB-based classification, this approach enables pixel-level segmentation, allowing further analysis such as estimating crack area or shape. The use of thermal imagery also makes the system robust to poor lighting conditions, enabling inspections in shaded or nighttime environments where RGB performance may degrade.

However, thermal sensing does come with limitations. It generally offers lower spatial resolution compared to RGB cameras and can be influenced by ambient temperature, humidity, or material properties. As a result, thermal segmentation is best used in conjunction with RGB imagery for cross-validation. In the current implementation, the IR-based segmentation mask is displayed independently on the dashboard for manual comparison. Automatic alignment and overlay with the RGB camera view will be introduced once physical sensor calibration is completed on the deployed robot.

By integrating thermal segmentation with optical classification, the system improves crack detection reliability across diverse structural and environmental conditions.

5.3 MQ-135 Gas Sensor – Hazard Classification:

To support environmental monitoring during inspections, the system includes a gas sensing module conceptually based on the MQ-135 semiconductor gas sensor. This sensor is sensitive to a broad range of air quality-related gases, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), ammonia (NH₃), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), sulfur-based compounds, and smoke particulates [10]. Although the physical sensor is not yet integrated into the climbing robot, the data processing and hazard classification pipeline has been fully developed and tested using synthetic and publicly available gas concentration datasets.

The core of the module is a lightweight Random Forest classifier [22] trained on a curated dataset (MQ135SensorData.csv) containing labeled gas concentration patterns across multiple scenarios (e.g., “Normal air,” “Elevated CO₂,” “Ammonia presence”). The model analyzes a sliding time window of recent readings to predict the most likely environmental condition. In parallel, a threshold-based alerting system is implemented to trigger immediate warnings when critical gas levels are exceeded, for instance, a CO₂-equivalent value above 1000 ppm [23].

To improve reliability and reduce signal noise, preprocessing techniques such as smoothing filters and outlier suppression are applied to the simulated sensor inputs. While the MQ-135 is not highly selective for individual gases, pattern recognition across temporal data enables reasonably accurate classification of general hazard types. This approach balances simplicity with responsiveness, allowing the system to flag environmental risks in real time.

During simulation, when a gas anomaly is detected, the dashboard displays a visual warning banner (e.g., “WARNING: Elevated CO₂ detected”) and dynamically updates a time-series plot of concentration trends. All alerts and gas readings are timestamped and logged, enabling post-inspection review and correlation with crack detection results from the visual and thermal pipelines.

Once the physical robot integration is complete, the system will support direct ingestion of real MQ-135 sensor outputs, seamlessly connecting to the same AI modules and dashboard logic. This staged development ensures the gas analysis component is robust and field-ready in advance of hardware deployment.

Table 2: Sensor modalities integrated in the platform, with their data types and AI models. Each model is trained on domain-specific data to recognize cracks or gas anomalies.

Sensor Modality	Primary Data	Trained AI Model	Dataset Used (examples)
Optical RGB Camera	2D color images (live)	MobileNetV2 classifier (crack vs no-crack)	SDNET2018 concrete crack dataset [24] (56k images); others for fine-tuning
Thermal IR Camera	Thermal images (heatmap)	U-Net segmentation (crack mask)	Maguire <i>et al.</i> crack segmentation dataset [7] (thermal crack labels)
MQ-135 Gas Sensor	Gas concentration (analog voltage)	Random Forest classifier / Threshold logic (gas anomaly type)	MQ-135 readings (MQ135SensorData.csv); specs indicating detection of NH ₃ , CO ₂ , etc.[10]

6. Crack Detection Workflow

The system performs parallel crack detection using both RGB and thermal camera inputs, processed in real time via the AI modules described in Section 4. To enable effective monitoring, the platform combines pre-processing, detection, quantification, and alerting in an integrated pipeline.

Image Acquisition and Pre-processing: Images are sourced from simulation datasets representing RGB and thermal modalities. RGB frames are resized to 160×160 pixels and normalized before classification. Thermal frames are processed as grayscale heatmaps for segmentation, with color maps applied only for display. Alignment is currently manual, with automatic calibration planned for future deployment.

Crack Detection and Quantification: RGB frames are classified using a MobileNetV2 model (see Section 4.1), producing binary predictions and confidence scores. High-confidence detections are visualized using optional overlays such as Grad-CAM. Thermal images are segmented using a U-Net model (see Section 4.2), producing binary crack masks. Morphological filtering removes artifacts, and skeletonization enables estimation of crack length, width, and area (in pixels). These metrics support crack severity ranking but are not yet converted into physical units due to lack of camera calibration.

Fusion and Alerting Logic: While automatic overlay of optical and thermal results is pending calibration, the dashboard currently displays both outputs side-by-side for manual cross-validation. Alerts are issued when cracks are detected, with ranked metrics and visual banners. Color-coded severity levels are based on pixel metrics, not physical measurements.

Tracking and Longitudinal Monitoring: Each crack detection event is timestamped, stored with associated metrics, and linked to the original image ID. This metadata allows future tracking of crack growth over time, pending spatial localization support in the robot platform.

Real-Time Performance: All inference modules were tested under simulated real-time conditions. On average, the RGB classifier processed a frame in ~ 0.4 seconds, thermal segmentation in ~ 0.57 seconds, and gas anomaly detection in ~ 0.08 seconds. These latencies support interactive, near-live dashboard performance. **Table 3** summarizes sample inference times and detection results for each modality during a representative monitoring session.

Table 3. Sample Inference Times and Detection Outcomes

Timestamp	Sensor Type	Inference Time (s)	Detection	Result
00:00	Optical	0.4	Crack	Detected
00:02	Infrared	0.57	Crack	Detected
00:04	Gas	0.08	Anomaly	Not Detected

Dashboard Interface and Alert Management: The dashboard interface is designed to present real-time outputs from all three sensing modalities in a cohesive and intuitive layout. It consists of dedicated panels for optical, thermal, and gas detection:

- **Optical Detection Panel:** Displays RGB images with detected cracks overlaid as semi-transparent red masks generated by the MobileNetV2 classifier. Each detection is timestamped and associated with pixel-based metrics, including crack length, width, and area.
- **Infrared Detection Panel:** Shows thermal images with U-Net-based segmentation masks overlaid on grayscale or pseudo-colored frames. While RGB-IR fusion overlays are under development, the current interface enables side-by-side comparison for manual cross-validation.
- **Gas Detection Panel:** Presents a live trend plot of gas concentration values from the MQ-135 sensor. Threshold-based warnings (e.g., “Elevated CO₂ Levels Detected”) are prominently displayed, and classifications from the Random Forest model are shown when confidence is high.

To reduce cognitive load, alerts from all modalities are centralized. When multiple anomalies occur, such as a detected crack and a gas spike, each is highlighted in its respective panel, and a unified notification banner ensures comprehensive situational awareness.

All events are timestamped and logged, allowing inspectors to review inspection history and correlate findings across modalities. While spatial mapping is not yet supported, timestamps and filenames currently serve as inspection proxies, paving the way for future localization and automated alignment.

7. Discussion and Contributions

While this study presents a fully implemented real-time dashboard for AI-powered infrastructure inspection, it is important to acknowledge the current limitations and assumptions, especially given that the climbing robot is still under development. All evaluations were conducted using publicly available datasets and simulated sensor inputs rather than real-world, on-robot data. This limits the ability to fully validate the end-to-end performance of the system under operational conditions.

Dataset constraints introduce notable limitations. For instance, the MobileNetV2 classifier was trained on the SDNET2018 dataset, which includes labeled RGB images of concrete cracks but lacks metadata such as scale, angle, or environmental variability. Similarly, the U-Net model for IR segmentation was trained on thermal imagery from previous studies, but thermal conditions in the field (e.g., sun exposure, wind, moisture) may produce significantly noisier inputs. These datasets do not fully capture the complexities of real inspections, such as camera motion blur, uneven lighting, or sensor misalignment during robot operation.

Because the system has not yet been deployed in a physical inspection environment, the fusion of sensor inputs is not spatially aligned or calibrated. Currently, the dashboard displays crack classifications, thermal segmentations, and gas readings side-by-side, but without spatial fusion or automatic correlation. This limits the utility of multi-modal interpretation in complex scenarios where defects may only appear in one modality (e.g., gas leaks without visible cracks).

The gas anomaly detection module is another area of limited realism. While a Random Forest classifier was trained on a curated dataset of MQ-135 readings, the sensor itself is known to be non-specific and sensitive to many ambient conditions. Moreover, without real-world data collection using the robot-mounted sensor, it is unclear how reliable the alerts will be in outdoor or mixed-gas environments.

From a system architecture perspective, real-time performance is achieved by transmitting sensor data from the robot over Wi-Fi to an external computer, where lightweight AI models are executed within a custom dashboard. This setup reflects the intended operational workflow, where the robot focuses on data collection and mobility, while inference and visualization are handled externally to reduce computational load on the onboard hardware. The Raspberry Pi 3B is currently used for control and communication tasks, but not for AI model inference. While this approach ensures responsiveness and flexibility during development, future deployments may consider partial or full on-board processing if compute resources, and power constraints allow.

Despite these limitations, this work contributes a reproducible and modular framework for integrating multi-modal sensor data (RGB, IR, gas) into an AI-enabled dashboard for non-destructive testing. The system demonstrates that low-latency inference pipelines and user-friendly interfaces can be developed ahead of full hardware readiness, enabling early-stage testing and iterative refinement. Going forward, key enhancements will include real sensor calibration, real-environment data collection, on-site processing evaluation, and longitudinal tracking of defect evolution across repeated inspection cycles.

8. Conclusion and Future Work

This work presented a real-time, AI-powered dashboard for infrastructure inspection, combining RGB, thermal, and gas sensing. The MobileNetV2 classifier achieved 91% accuracy and 0.87 precision for crack detection on SDNET2018, while the U-Net model enabled pixel-level segmentation from thermal images. Inference latencies were kept below 0.6 seconds per frame, ensuring smooth live operation.

Gas anomaly detection using a Random Forest model and MQ-135 data provided real-time classification with under 100 ms response time. Unlike traditional systems limited to a single modality or offline processing, our system offers synchronized, multi-modal detection and visual alerts in real time.

Future work includes spatial calibration between RGB and IR views, real-environment validation on bridges and facades, and integration of more advanced models and sensors, while maintaining real-time performance. The system provides a reproducible foundation for scalable, AI-enabled NDT platforms aligned with Industry 4.0 goals.

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All data and source code necessary to reproduce the results presented in this paper are openly available and adhere to the F.A.I.R. data principles. They can be accessed via the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/gheزالahmad/NDT-Rover>

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Appendix

Figure 3a. Real-time gas concentration monitoring interface. The dashboard displays predicted gas type, sensor readings across multiple gas channels, and corresponding confidence scores in tabular form. A time-series plot visualizes trends with threshold indicators for critical gas levels, enabling real-time environmental hazard alerts.

Figure 3b. Optical camera crack detection module. The dashboard presents high-resolution surface images with per-frame crack classification. Summary statistics include average crack area, length, and width in pixels, supporting quantitative surface assessment over time.

◆ Infrared Camera

Figure 3c. Infrared camera segmentation interface. Thermal images are processed using a U-Net segmentation model, and predicted crack regions are outlined in red. The dashboard enables manual review of crack shape and distribution under varying thermal contrast conditions.